

THE PREPARATION AND STUDY OF FLAME RETARDANT FOR EXPANDABLE POLYSTYRENE

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ABSTRACT

A composite flame retardant for expandable polystyrene(EPS) was reported, in which phenol formaldehyde resin (PF)was used as coating agent, graphite oxide(GO)was used as flame retardant. The GO was prepared by means of the Hummer method, the mixture of GO and formaldehyde were fully dispersed by ultrasonic processing, then phenol was added into the mixture. The coating agent of graphite oxide and phenolic resin (GO-PF) was prepared by intercalation and polymerization of phenol and formaldehyde in GO. GO-PF was blended with EPS as a kind of flame retardant.

1 INTRODUCTION

EPS is widely used in building insulating material, because it has the advantages of lightweight and low heat conductivity. However, conventional EPS with hollow foam pore structure may produce large amount of heat (about 1300kW/m²) and collapse easily, when it is exposed to naked flame, which would make the buildings in danger of fire. The study of combustion process of EPS showed that it turned into combustible alkanes, which lowered the ignition of EPS and made its burning rate reach up to 400mm/min^[1-2].

In order to obtain a safe, reliable and thermal insulation EPS, all sorts of flame retardant agents are usually introduced to EPS to improve its flame-retardant property. The mechanism of flame retardant can be divided into two categories. One of the mechanism is that flame retardant can capture free radicals, and prevent the generation of small molecule alkanes. These flame retardant mainly includes halogenated flame retardants, phosphorous flame retardants ^[3], hexabromocyclododecane^[4],

tetrabromo ring octane^[5], decabrominated diphenyl oxide^[6], and TRIS (β -chloroethyl) phosphate^[7] etc. The other one is that flame retardant can form a covering layer by lowering the surface temperature of burning material to achieve retardant effect, such as magnesium hydroxide^[8] etc.

Since the halogen flame retardants have better compatibility with polystyrene (PS), it was often used for flame retardant of EPS. However, in nowadays many countries strictly prohibit or restrict the use of halogen flame retardants because they produce the toxic substances, which may directly threat to life safety in the field of fire. GO is an ideal flame retardant agent, which can produce more char, little toxic gas, and form stable superstratum on building insulating material when GO burns. But the compatibility of GO and EPS is very poor. The application of graphite is limited because it is neither hydrophilic nor oleophilic. If EPS granules are coated by the mixture of PF and GO, the compatibility between GO and EPS will be improved.

In this paper, the composite flame retardant containing PF and GO for EPS is reported. The flame retardant property of EPS composite material can be improved by using PF as coating agent and GO as flame retardant.

2 EXPERIMENTAL AND CHARACTERIZATION

2.1 Materials

Natural flake graphite (GP, 200mesh) was purchased from Qingdao, China. Concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) was obtained from Guan County, China. Sodium nitrate($NaNO_3$), Potassium permanganate($KMnO_4$), phenol, Sodium hydroxide($NaOH$), Polyethylene glycol(PEG), Twain-60, P-toluene sulfonic acid were purchased from Tianjin, China. Formaldehyde was provided by Shenyang, China. EPS(0.9mm-1.4mm) was purchased from Panjin, China.

2.2 Preparation of coating agent GO-PF using in-situ polymerization

The graphite oxide was prepared by means of the Hummer method. The mixture of concentrated H_2SO_4 , $NaNO_3$ and $KMnO_4$ were added to a 500ml reaction kettle equipped with a mechanical stirred and a condenser. The mixture was stirred for 30min at $35^\circ C$. Then deionized water were added into the reaction kettle. The mixture was heated to $98^\circ C$ and was kept constant temperature stirring for 30 min. After filtration of the mixture, GO was obtained. The resulting GO and formaldehyde in a sample bottle were put into ultrasonic generator and make sure that GO was dispersed in formaldehyde solution, then phenol and $NaOH$ was added into the mixture. The reaction was carried out at $85^\circ C$ for 5h, the product GO-PF was got. The composition in feed for preparing GO-PF with different GO ratio is shown in the Table1.

Table 1: The composition in feed for preparing GO-PF with different GO ratio.

	GO-PF(I)	GO-PF(II)	GO-PF(III)	GO-PF(IV)
GO	5.0g	10.0g	15.0g	20.0g
Phenol	41.8g	41.8g	41.8g	41.8g
Formaldehyde	58.2g	58.2g	58.2g	58.2g
NaOH	3.0g	3.0g	3.0g	3.0g

2.3 Preparation of coating agent GO/PF using blending method

Formaldehyde and phenol solution were added and mixed in a reaction kettle in the $85^\circ C$ water bath. And then Sodium hydroxide was added into the reaction kettle. After finishing the reaction, PF was obtained. Finally, the blend coating agent of GO / PF was prepared by adding GO into the PF product.

2.4 Preparation of GO-PF/EPS composite material

The GO-PF/EPS composite material were prepared via two steps, prefoam and secondary foam forming. Prefoam included steam foam and ripening process. The density, strength, and insulation performance of the material depend on the prefoam time, prefoam temperature, ripening time and

ripening temperature. Prefoam is carried out at steam foaming for 4 min , curing for 4h at 40 °C , the overall performance of the resulting material is the best. The prefoam EPS was mixed with GO-PF, the film former(PEG), surface active agent(Tween-60) and curing agent(P-toluene sulfonic acid TsOH). The GO-PF/EPS composite material was prepared by secondary molding foam. The results of the composite materials are shown in the Table2.

Table 2: The mass ratio of EPS and GO-PF

Mass ratio	GO-PF(I)	GO-PF(II)	GO-PF(III)	GO-PF(IV)
EPS:GO-PF	1:1	1:1	1:1	1:1
EPS:GO-PF	1:2	1:2	1:2	1:2
EPS:GO-PF	1:3	1:3	1:3	1:3
EPS:GO-PF	1:4	1:4	1:4	1:4
EPS:GO-PF	1:5	1:5	1:5	1:5

2.5 Characterizations of GO-PF/EPS composite material

Thermogravimetric(TG) was used to test stability of GO-PF under heating rate 10°C/min, by Netzsch STA 449 F3 thermal analyzer.

The oxygen index was tested by JF-3 oxygen index detector depended on ASTM-D2863 method. The sample dimension is 120mm×10 mm×10mm. The rate of the mix gas is 10mL/min.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were recorded by Hitachi S-4300.

The flame retardant grade was evaluated by M607 combustion analyzer depended on UL94-vertical burning. The sample dimension is 150mm×50 mm×13mm.

The mechanical property of the GO-PF/EPS composite material was confirmed by WSM-20KN universal testing machine. The compressive sample dimension is 50mm×13mm×13mm, and the compression rate is 20mm/min, the compression ratio is 50%.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Compatibility analysis of GO and PF

Figure 1: Compatibility of GP/PF(a) and GO/PF(b)

The mixture of GP/PF was deposited for 72h, stratification phenomenon took place, as shown in Figure 1a. Simultaneously, the GO/PF was deposited in the same conditions, the stratification phenomenon didn't appear between graphite oxide and Phenol formaldehyde resin (Figure 1b). As a result, graphite oxide and Phenol formaldehyde resin are compatible.

3.2 Determination of preparation method

Figure 2: TG cures of GO-PF and GO/PF

Figure 2 is the TG cures of compound GO-PF and GO/PF, the ratio of GO to PF in GO/PF and GO-PF is exactly the same. The results show that with increasing the heat temperature, thermal weight loss of GO / PF is always greater than GO-PF. Therefore, GO-PF is better than GO / PF in thermal stability.

Figure 3: Images of cured GO-PF (a) and GO / PF (b)

As shown in Figure 3, the compound (GO-PF) cured by in-situ polymerization is more dense and uniform than the compound (GO / PF) cured by blending method. In summary, in-situ polymerization is selected to prepare GO-PF.

3.3 Flame retardant performance of GO-PF/EPS composite material

3.3.1 Limiting oxygen index (LOI) of GO-PF/ EPS composite material

The oxygen indexes of GO-PF/ EPS composite material are shown in Figure 4, GO-PF/ EPS composite material was prepared in various mass ratios of GO-PF and EPS.

Figure 4: LOI figure of GO-PF/EPS composite material

Limiting oxygen index shows a rising trend with the increase of mass ratio of GO-PF and EPS, and with the increase of proportion of GO in the GO-PF. The flame retardant performance of EPS is improved obviously by introducing the GO-PF. By increasing the mass of GO-PF, the coating layers on EPS beads surface get thickened. When it burns, the higher density fixed carbon layer would be produced, which make the effect of flame retardant of materials better.

3.3.2 Combustion grade of GO-PF/ EPS composite material

Table 3: Combustion grade of GO-PF/ EPS composite material

The mass ratio of EPS and GO-PF	GO/ GO-PF=5%	GO/ GO-PF=10%	GO/ GO-PF=15%	GO/ GO-PF=20%
EPS:GO-PF=1:0.0	—	—	—	—
EPS:GO-PF=1:0.5	—	—	—	—
EPS:GO-PF=1:1.0	—	—	—	V-1
EPS:GO-PF=1:1.5	—	—	V-1	V-0
EPS:GO-PF=1:2.0	—	V-1	V-0	V-0
EPS:GO-PF=1:2.5	—	V-1	V-0	V-0

The combustion grade of GO-PF/ EPS composite material are listed in table 3. When EPS:GO-PF $\geq 1:2.0$, proportion of GO in the GO-PF not less than 15%, and EPS:GO-PF $\geq 1:1.5$, proportion of GO in the GO-PF not less than 20%, the vertical burning grade of UL94 reaches V-0. This result indicated that dripping phenomenon do not happen when material burns, which prevent from the fire expansion.

3.3.3 SEM analysis of conflagrant residual carbon of GO-PF/EPS composite material

Figure 5: SEM images of conflagrant residual carbon of EPS coated with Phenolic resin (a) and GO-PF/EPS composite material(b)

Figure 5a represent SEM micrographs of conflagrant residual carbon of EPS coated with Phenolic resin. Carbon residue paries is thin. The image of conflagrant residual carbon of GO-PF/EPS composite material is shown in Figure 5b. Carbon residue paries is relatively thick and dense. Material surface is covered by the carbon residue, which can effectively isolate oxygen and reduce the material surface temperature.

3.4 Compression performance test of GO-PF / EPS composite material

Figure 6: Compression performance of GO-PF / EPS composite material

The compression performance of the GO-PF / EPS composite material is shown in Figure 6. For the GO-PF / EPS, the compressive strength of PF is the biggest, the EPS beads is the smallest. Therefore with the increasing of proportion of GO-PF in the GO-PF / EPS, the compressive strength of composite material raises.

With the increasing of proportion of GO in the GO-PF, compressive strength of GO-PF / EPS composite presents a declining trend. When proportion of GO-PF and EPS is fixed, the increasing of proportion of GO in the GO-PF, the decrease of mass of PF lead to the reduction of compressive strength.

3.5 Thermal insulation performance of GO-PF / EPS composite material

Figure 7: Thermal insulation performance of the GO-PF/EPS composite material

The impact of the component of the GO-PF/EPS composite material on thermal conductivity index is shown in Figure 7. With the increasing of proportion of GO-PF in the GO-PF/EPS, and the increasing of proportion of GO in the GO-PF, thermal conductivity index of the GO-PF/EPS composite material raise. It is because that thermal conductivity index of EPS is the smallest in three components. In order to assure the good thermal insulation performance of GO-PF/EPS composite material, the proportion of GO and PF should be limited in a certain range.

4 CONCLUSIONS

EPS with GO-PF shows the excellent flame retardancy. The performances are enhanced to LOI 29.8, UL94, and V-0. This kind of material has not only good self-extinguish effect but also non melt and dript phenomena, and can form char when it burning. The EPS/GO-PF composites have favourable mechanical behavior and heat-insulating property.

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